

BREADCRUMB

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and Innovation programme under the agreement No. 101136701

DELIVERABLE D5.4

Dissemination and Communication activities - (1)

Project title	BRinging Evidence-bAseD food Chain solutions to prevent and RedUce food waste related to Marketing standards, and deliver climate and circularity co Benefits		
Project acronym	BREADCRUMB		
Call topic	HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01		
Type of action	HORIZON-RIA		
Coordinator	EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK - EV ILVO		
Project number	101136701		
Project start date	01/01/2024	Duration	36 months
URL	https://www.breadcrumb-project.eu/		

D5. 4 - DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES - (1)

Due date	31/12/2024	Delivery date	17/12/2024
Work package	WP5		
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Version	03		
Dissemination level	Public		

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VERSION AND AMENDMENTS HISTORY

Version	Date (MM/DD/YYYY)	Created /Amended by	Changes
00	13/08/2024	Edgar Valverde	Table of Contents
01	29/11/2024	Marisol Fernández, Edgar Valverde	First draft
02	13/12/2024	Marisol Fernández, María Jiménez, Edgar Valverde	Second versión, updates figures
03	17/12/2024	María Jiménez, Edgar Valverde	Reviewed version by ILVO.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AB	Agent Based
BMSIG	Breadcrumb Marketing Standards Interest Group
CA	Consortium Agreement
CS	Case Study
CSOs	Civil Society Organizations
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility

D&C&E (or CDE/DCE)	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation
D&C (or C&D)	Dissemination and Communication
DECP	Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EM	Exploitation Manager
EU	European Union
FC	Food Chain
FLW	Food Loss & Waste
FW	Food Waste
GA	General assembly
GA	Grant Agreement
GIM	Gender Issue Manager
HEU	Horizon European
IP(R)	Intellectual Property (Rights)
MS	Member State
PC	Project Coordinator
R&I	Research & Innovation
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
RPG	Role Playing Game
RTOs	Research & Technology Organisations
SC	Supply Chain
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TCB	Technical Coordination Board
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VASP	Value-Added Surplus Products
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is developed in the framework of the Work Package 5: Research and Innovation scale-up. The main objective of the Deliverable 5.4 is to report Dissemination and Communication activities undertaken during the first year of the project. More specifically, it provides details on:

- The project branding and all the channels and materials that have been designed and established for BREADCRUMB.
- The main communication activities to reach out general audiences, including the posts on social media channels and dedicated campaigns.
- The dissemination activities to engage with targeted stakeholders using the project's website, participation in events and publications.

All partners have participated in these activities for effective and maximised outreach of the project, being the project website and LinkedIn the most impactful channels by now. Newsletter and X and YouTube accounts require still some efforts to exploit their potential. The synergies between partners knowledge, the solid project branding and the interaction between different platforms will contribute to this goal.

Looking forward, the consortium will prioritise:

- Expand the work carried out so far to maintain and increase the relevance of channels.
- Complete specific actions like the project newsletters and the official project video.
- Showcase project concepts and achievements across different environments to maximise awareness on FLW and the impact of project activities.

This deliverable is the first report of C&D activities, submitted by M12 of project execution (December 2024) and will be updated every year until the end of the project in D5.5 and D5.6.

1 INTRODUCTION – BREADCRUMB COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN AND LINKS TO PROJECT ACTIVITIES

1.1 BREADCRUMB Project Overview

The BREADCRUMB project aims to provide an empirical evidence-based understanding of the purpose and nature of food marketing standards, their impact on FW generation, and based on this evidence, propose interventions that strike a balance between reducing FW and the other objectives pursued by these standards. Furthermore, the project strives to improve market access for suboptimal foods by guiding food businesses to select appropriate marketing channels, and by fostering change in consumers’ acceptance of suboptimal foods. All of this information will be structured into operational and policy guidance on how to prevent / reduce FW related to marketing standards.

More specifically, the Grant Agreement defines the following **procedure for the project**: "(i) establish a holistic view of marketing standards and identify those with key relevance to FW generation; (ii) create evidence-based estimates of FW generated as a consequence of marketing standards; (iii) provide solutions that alleviate the negative impacts of marketing standards on FW, based on a valid understanding of the underlying mechanisms of FW generation and trade-offs with other objectives (re-balancing marketing standards); (iv) enhance the business potential of "sub-optimal" foods; (v) inform and guide food businesses, consumers, owners of standards and policy regulators on how to prevent/reduce FW related to marketing standards".¹

Figure 1. The BREADCRUMB project at a glance. Source: BREADCRUMB Grant Agreement, Part B, page 101 (electronic version).

To achieve these common objectives, BREADCRUMB project counts with a solid Communication and Dissemination plan, with measurable KPIs and specific channels to be fulfilled. With this

purpose, the **D&C core group** validates and enhances the activities for sharing the information with the public and interested stakeholders.

1.2 Mapping BREADCRUMB Outputs

BREADCRUMB Communication and Dissemination plan was introduced first in D5.1, this section reflects how the deliverable fits in BREADCRUMB's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to BREADCRUMB's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

BREADCRUMB GA Component Title	BREADCRUMB GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D5.1 Dissemination, Communication and exploitation plan - (1)	A detailed plan for the dissemination will be provided on M6 in alignment with the project's activities. The progress of the activities will be reported in D5.4, D5.5 and D5.6.	Chapters 3, 4 and 6	Chapter 3 and 4 - Communication and dissemination structure: includes the project identity, tools and channels. Chapter 6 – Internal activities to promote.
	Will include a plan for synergies with other projects	Chapter 5	This chapter summarises the performed and planning activities for synergies with other projects.
TASKS – Links to the C&D plan and to this deliverable			
T5.1 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan (DECP)	Communications will incorporate innovative methods for sharing information with the public and interested stakeholders in accordance with the strategy.	Chapters 3 and 4	Chapter 3 and 4 include the D&C activities.
T5.2 Dissemination and Communication activities	Visibility of the project activities will be ensured through a number of traditional and electronic communication tools (section 2.2.1). Activities include: i) development of	Chapters 3 and 4	It includes the tools and channels used to communicate and disseminate the project

	<p>project identity/brand (logos, colours, font sets, banners, etc.), brochures, press releases, roll-up, factsheets, leaflets, and similar resources to support partners in publicizing the project, (ii) the creation of the project's public website and material sharing portal in M3; (iii) social media groups setup and activities (e.g. videos, LinkedIn, X, YouTube); (iv) e-Newsletters and publications in trade and scientific journals, iv) gathering feedback from stakeholders through networking events</p>		
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2 BREADCRUMB COMMUNICATION TOOLS AND ACTIVITIES

2.1 Project identity

During the first months of the project the BREADCRUMB project identity was created. The final version of promotional material, available for the partners, was delivered and accordingly reported in D5.1. The available material until M12 and the updates are indicated as follows:

- Logo
- Brand guidelines
- Project templates
- Deliverable and reporting template
- Presentation template
- Collection of pictures on the topics related to BREADCRUMB.
- Promotional material

2.2 Presentation of BREADCRUMB’s promotional material

- **Roll-up:** being updated the latest version to reinforce the uniform visibility of the consortium among the partners activities.

Figure 2.- BREADCRUMB roll-up version 3

- **Leaflet:**

Figure 3. Leaflet sample

- **Factsheet:** latest version including a QR code leading to project’s website:

Figure 4. BREADCRUMB factsheet.

- **Slide deck:** Not included in the KPIs but produced for reinforcement of the communication activities.

Figure 5. Slidedeck introductory slide.

- **Promotional videos:** 9 videos for the campaign “Meet the partners” have been produced so far and are available in their respective section on project website:

Figure 6. Example of a 'meet the partner' video on the project website.

2.3 Social media

Metrics and KPIs of the development of the social media channels are described in the following sections and Section 6, including the impact in reference to the general KPIs of D&C.

2.3.1 LinkedIn

Figure 7. Overview of BREADCRUMB's LinkedIn page.

The total count of followers to date (as of 2024/12/15) of the page is 432 with a total of 62 posts published. Figure 8 below present the impact metrics of the publications, demonstrating how LinkedIn is clearly the main route to generate attraction to project activities.

Figure 8.- LinkedIn metrics.

2.3.2 X

Figure 9.- Frontpage of X

The total count of followers to date (2024/12/15) of the page is 210 with a total of 34 posts published.

2.3.3 YouTube

The total count of subscribers is 23 to date (2024/12/15). More support to partners have been requested to increase the impact of the project video channels.

BREADCRUMB activity in YouTube channel has been reinforced thanks to the production of different videos introducing BC partners. Until the moment 9 videos have been published, being the links and the partners described as follows:

- ILVO → <https://youtu.be/yFOm-rHZcHw?si=62o4WDM6Tp63RLfg>
- VLTN → https://youtu.be/o5jqV6Ve5go?si=SDZ4J_iXOA7BkkDR
- UCPH → https://youtu.be/QJakyKieDK8?si=1JOFDgg_kePueNzp
- CSCP → <https://youtu.be/s9qBmjKTu1w?si=b5ugc2OyCrVQBF9J>
- AINIA → <https://youtu.be/ThfuQt6r1WA?si=1G-CDkyvbJSSVU>
- CREDA → <https://youtu.be/coZUIFIMvgo?si=oKOubhzsrTdwVVg9>
- MENSANA → <https://youtu.be/yGxbPZ2xBzc?si=AJPv2gTHrHG7OID7>
- MC- SONAE → <https://youtube.com/shorts/JPM4E9eEyPE?si=tGWkULrPDjOu-2sF>
- AVEC → <https://youtube.com/shorts/LH2EZ4xS1j0?si=wAkFdpkl4BtSixME>

The integration of videos in the project website is expected to attract further views and attention to the YouTube channel.

Figure 10.- Videos and shorts available at BREADCRUMB YouTube profile

2.4 Dedicated campaigns

BREADCRUMB has designed different social media campaigns to maximise project visibility leveraging on partners’ networks and specific trending.

1. **MEET THE PARTNERS:** Presenting project partners with their own videos (linked to the website and YouTube).

Figure 11. Summary of the meet the partners videos on LinkedIn.

2. **JARGON AND BASIC BREADCRUB INFO:** To provide further context on the project activities and marketing standards:

Figure 12. Example of jargon video on FMS.

- 3. SELECTED DAYS:** As will be further mentioned in 3.2 (due to the links on events participation and links to other initiatives), participating in selected days help maximise the project visibility while also expressing how the project contributes to, for example, on IDAFLW (September 27th).

3 BREADCRUMB DISSEMINATION TOOLS AND ACTIVITIES

3.1 Website

The website was launched on month 3 of the project (March 2024). It provides an overview of the objectives and programme of work to track its progress and present relevant results. The website is publicly available and serves as a useful source of information for the relevant audience and other stakeholders. BREADCRUMB structure was already described in D5.1 but, as content and maintenance are continuously updated during the duration of the project, D5.4 and the next deliverables reporting communication and dissemination activities will update the changes and updates in the webpage: <https://www.breadcrumb-project.eu/>

Figure 13. Project website.

The continuous update of news and events has a positive impact in the number of page views, being currently 210 users:

Figure 14.- Website analytics until M11.

3.1.1.1 News

13 pieces of news have been published from the launch of the website: <https://www.breadcrumb-project.eu/news-events/>

Every piece of news is accompanied by image support, being detailed as follows:

Figure 15. Examples of news on BREADCRUMB's website.

3.1.1.2 Newsletter subscription

Newsletter is an important tool to inform different stakeholders about the project activities and advances. Multiple access points have been included on the website to maximise the newsletter audience, including a *subscription pop-up* and a dedicated button accessible at all times (presented in Figure 16).

Figure 16.- Newsletter highlights in BREADCRUMB website (pop-up left, newsletter button right).

The first project newsletter was issued by June 2024 and is available through the project website: [link](#). Newsletter #2 will be issued during January 2025. Number of subscribers to date (2024/12/17) is 72.

3.1.1.3 New sections

As networking is one of the main pillars of the D&C activities, BREADCRUMB website has included two additional sub-sections under related project:

- BREADCRUMB External Advisory Board (EAB).
- Food Marketing Standard Interest Group (FMSIG).

These sections are still on test mode when this deliverable is being prepared, since not all details of the individuals involved are available, and will be publicly available soon.

Figure 17.- FMSIG participants included under the correspondent website section.

3.1.1.4 Other content included

As mentioned in section 2, with the objective of increasing the impact of the videos produced under “Meet the partners” campaign, the link to the YouTube videos have been embedded in the partners presentation.

Besides, the first public results of the project are also available, and website users can download the inventory of FMS directly from the results page: <https://www.breadcrumb-project.eu/results/>

Figure 18. View of the results page on BREADCRUMB's website.

3.2 Events and Special days

BREADCRUMB partners are active in participating in national and international events and conferences. PNO tracks the attendance in these events, being some of them the following:

- Reduzierung von Lebensmittelverschwendung durch Abbau von ästhetischen Standards bei Obst und Gemüse: Hindernisse, Potenziale, Lösungsansätze. Organised by DUH.
- ADA University and University of Bologna, Joint Certificate Program: Workshop titled "Food Losses and Waste in Horticultural Systems: The BREADCRUMB Project".
- Executive program in Sustainable Horticultural Systems".
- EuroFRI AISBL's Food Forum 2024.
- Seafood Expo.
- MACFRUT 2024.
- Joint webinar with WASTELESS and FOLOU projects "Current developments in Food Loss & Waste reduction".
- "Set-up an alliance to improve FLW measuring and monitoring: participants, goals, approach and methods" (Roundtable).
- "Event Let's Reduce Consumer Food Waste!.
- Solutions from the European Consumer Food Waste Forum "
- Fruit Attraction 2024.

Furthermore, dedicated posts and communication activities were designed for specific days and events with specific interest for BREADCRUMB. These events and special days were published across the social media, aimed to be also shared with the partners.

- 30 March 2024: International Day of Zero Waste | United Nations
- 24 April 2024: Stop Food Waste Day 2024
- 27 September 2024: The International Day of Awareness of Food Loss and Waste (IDAFLW),
- 16 October 2024: World_Food_Day

Figure 19.- BC promotions on BC social media.

3.3 Publications

BREADCRUMB has already an account on FoodNavigator to **disseminate** results, articles, upon acceptance.

Furthermore, the first BREADCRUMB newsletter was launched in June 2024. The second newsletter is currently under development, being gathered the inputs from the partners. This communication tool has been reinforced through the pop-up subscription included in the BREADCRUMB website, aimed to reach a higher number of subscribers.

BREADCRUMB is aware of the importance of using the tools provided by the EC, the industry and the scientific community, using the EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub platform for 3 publications, available at https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/food_waste/eu-food-loss-waste-prevention-hub/ as shown:

Root	Resource	ID	Status	Date	Filter mode
7137	Collaboration opportunity: your input on private food marketing standards	2	VALIDATED	Wednesday 07 of August 2024	Off
6436	BREADCRUMB project kick off meeting on 16-17 January	4	VALIDATED	Wednesday 07 of August 2024	Off
7585	Fruit Attraction Conference 2024 in Madrid on 9 October	5	VALIDATED	Wednesday 02 of October 2024	Off

Figure 20.- BREADCRUMB publications under EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub.

4 CLUSTERING AND COLLABORATION

BREADCRUMB is very active in clustering and collaboration with the sister project ROSETTA and other related projects. For tracking of every collaboration between the projects, PNO created a list of collaboration activities and other initiatives that are continuously updated:

- **Sister project ROSETTA & related projects ZERO, CHORIZO, WASTELESS, FOLOU, SISTERS.** Available information about the sister project and other related projects available under the section “[Related projects](#)”.

Figure 21.- List of related projects under BREADCRUMB website.

- **Collaborative Blog publication Website: How to Stop Food Waste collaborative blog**
This blog serves as a source of inspiration, demonstrating how collective endeavors can make significant strides in combating food waste. By featuring initiatives like BREADCRUMB, CHORIZO, SISTERS, WASTELESS, and ZeroW, the blog emphasizes the diverse

approaches being employed to tackle various aspects of the food waste crisis, ranging from marketing practices to systemic changes and waste reduction solutions.

<https://www.breadcrumb-project.eu/news/how-to-stop-food-waste-collaborative-blog/>

Figure 22.- Promotional posts for presenting sister projects.

- **Introducing Rosetta in BREADCRUMB website**

Introduction to the ROSETTA project explaining how ROSETTA focuses on reducing food waste related to marketing standards, while BREADCRUMB's objective is to create a comprehensive inventory of both private and public food marketing standards, understand their purpose and impact, and develop strategies to minimize food wastage.

Figure 23. ROSETTA's introduction post.

- **SISTERS x BREADCRUMB - Invitation to Speak at Our Annual Webinar titled “Reducing Food Waste in Retail: Balancing Profit and Sustainability.”**
 Speaker at the SISTERS upcoming annual webinar titled “Reducing Food Waste in Retail: Balancing Profit and Sustainability. Public webinar on October 17th 2024.
- **SISTERS-FOLOU-ROSETTA-BREADCRUMB collaboration**
 Collaboration Opportunity for Joint Campaign on Primary Production: “How synergies between various EU initiatives can raise awareness and combat food losses and waste at the agricultural level’.

Figure 24. Promotion on social networks (LinkedIn) of the joint campaign between SISTERS, FOLOU, ROSETTA and BREADCRUMB.

5 INTERNAL ACTIVITIES TO SUPPORT PARTNERS ON COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

Besides the activities linked to BREADCRUMB communication and dissemination, leader of WP5: PNO INNOVATION, held on the 20th of June, an internal training session on effectively promoting BREADCRUMB on social media. In this training there were shared tips and tools to maximize the impact of the activities through the Social Media channels:

Figure 25. Public post to promote the internal training on LinkedIn.

The key aspects covered in the internal training are the following:

- Main differences between Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities.
- BREADCRUMB's C&D KPIs and target audiences.
- BREADCRUMB on social media channels and proposed campaigns.
- Other tools available.
- Guidelines and EU disclaimer.

6 IMPACT OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES DURING THE 1ST YEAR OF THE PROJECT

Table 2 below shows the Key Performance Indicators to achieve at the end of BREADCRUMB project within all the activities included in the WP5 in collaboration with all partners. These KPIs were already described in D5.1

Table 2. BREADCRUMB KPIs.

Social media, website, videos		
	KPIs to achieve at M48	Status at M12
BREADCRUMB website	5,000 page views	210 users (number of users who interacted with your site or launched your app for the first time).
Social media (X, LinkedIn, YouTube)	>100 posts; >15,000 impressions per year	66 original posts without including the reposts with comments just in LinkedIn, 20 comments, 59 reposts 1880 page views. 726 unique visitors. 457 followers. 39 new followers in the last 30 days. 55639 impresions until M12. 1676 reactions.
Videos	4	9 videos (Meet the partners campaign)
Publications		
	KPIs to achieve at M48	Status at M12
BREADCRUMB newsletter	7	1 newsletter (June 2024) 2 nd Newsletter (in progress)
Informative material (Digital and printed format)	1 roll-up; 3,000 leaflets; 1,000 factsheets.	1 roll-up (no details on printed leaflets/factsheets)
Publications in local, national and international business journals e.g. Food Navigator, EuroNews, EUagenda and other journals in the food domain.	>20	1 press release

Practice Abstracts (EIP-AGRI format)	4	-
Project outputs disseminated on EC websites	5	3 publications
Peer-reviewed articles in industry magazines	>8	-
Peer-reviewed scientific papers when possible, on 'gold' (open access) or 'green' access	>10 accepted for publication	-
Events/activities		
	KPIs to achieve at M48	Status at M12
Final conference	150 participants, and 50 new connections	-
Project results presentations in national and EU conferences, seminars, trade shows (Foodexpo, Denmark, the largest food event in northern Europe; Anuga FoodTec, Germany; SIAL, France).	≥12 events attended and ≥12 presentations	7
Project promotion through professional networks (professional bodies, networks, trade associations and European Technology Platforms (ETPs))	>10 meetings	0
Participation at project events of direct contacts	>5 policy actors	0
Project presentations in scientific community and FW Expert Groups events	>5 events	0
Project contribution and agreements with the EU Platform on FLW, and the European Consumer Food Waste Forum (ECFWF) and JCR FW group.	>4 events; establishment of cooperation agreement with JRC	0
Educational packages (lectures, webinars, audio-visual material, etc.)	≥3 lectures, 450 students reached	2
Participation in broad events (Open day at the Universities, EU-MSCA Researchers' Nights, and Knowledge Open Festivals etc.)	≥10 events	1

7 CONCLUSIONS

This document reports the main C&D activities that have been executed by the BREADCRUMB consortium during the first year of project implementation. All partners contributed to them following the guidelines provided by PNO (through a content creation schedule for project channels) and their own motivations (inc. usage of company and personal channels and attendance to events).

The implementation of the C&D strategy presented by M6 has already started. The proposed channels have been actively used (specially the project website and LinkedIn). All these activities have contributed to increasing the project visibility, establishing the project's identity and stakeholder engagement. However, efforts are still required to reach broader audiences, specially in those channels that are not that relevant in terms of interaction.

The main focus for the coming months will be:

- Finalising the 2nd project newsletter by January 2025.
- Completing the first project official video.
- Maintaining and updating the C&D materials and channels.
- Monitoring and encouraging partner participation in C&D actions.

Looking ahead, the consortium will refine the efforts to showcase the findings and achievements, to leave a lasting impact on FLW reduction.